

**ANALYSIS OF THE TRANSLATION OF JACK LONDON'S WORKS INTO
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Abstract. *In the article illuminated the uniqueness of Jack London's work who was one of America's most advanced writers. And an analysis of their translation, with skillful way: translation of personal names, geographical names, and words that reflect national characteristics in the English-to-Uzbek translation of stories.*

Keywords: *transliteration, translation, translation analysis, chronotope, poetic means, image, allegory, symbol, epithet, metaphor, allegory, allusion, humor, mythology.*

**АНАЛИЗ ПЕРЕВОДА ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ ДЖЕКА ЛОНДОНА НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ
ЯЗЫК**

Аннотация. *В статье освещается уникальность произведений Джека Лондона и проводится анализ их перевода, в том числе искусного перевода личных имен, географических названий и слов, отражающих национальные особенности в англо-узбекском переводе рассказов.*

Ключевые слова: *транслитерация, перевод, переводческий анализ, хронотоп, поэтический носитель, образ, аллегория, символ, эпитет, метафора, аллегория, аллюзия, юмор, мифология.*

INTRODUCTION

After the independence of Uzbekistan, great changes took place in all aspects for the development of our country, and these reforms are ongoing. Such development and growth is evident in the field of education as well as in every field. At this point, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's "If you ask me what troubles you, I will answer that it is the education of our children".[8] Their opinions are proof of our opinion. In the current process of globalization, in order to teach the young generation foreign languages, to develop the system of training specialists who can speak these languages fluently, and in this process, to create conditions and opportunities for them to use the achievements of world civilization and world information resources effectively, to develop international cooperation and communication, foreign countries in our country a number of decisions were made to improve the teaching of languages, especially English.

In the rapidly developing world, international relations, the influence of their lives on each other, relations in various fields, exchanges of experience and ideas, harmony and synthesis have risen to a higher level than ever before. Any phenomenon can receive its true value only on a global scale. In literary studies, the principle of comparative evaluation of national literary works with rare examples of world word art is developing.

Consequently, the influence of advanced world literature on Uzbek literature had a significant impact from the end of the 19th century to the beginning of the 20th century. At the heart of socio-political changes, we can see the rise of the art of translation and mutual literary

relations, and the direct influence of the artistic way through Russian literature. A number of genres were formed and developed in Uzbek literature under the influence of world literature. At this point, it should be emphasized that the work translated from one language to another language improves the interaction of peoples, introduces the world view and culture of one people to another people. That's why in the artistic translation, giving the words reflecting the names of people, geographical names and national characteristics also has a special place.

TOPIC ANALYSIS

Jack London's works embody originality and naturalness, there is a huge arsenal of poetic tools, in particular, a special system of images that make up the idea and structure, the important features of the chronotope, the roles of the author, the narrator and the characters in the work. , a clear system of the image and its role in opposition, the role of allegories, symbols, epithets and metaphors, reference to irony, humor and humor, reference to historical events and mythological images taken from the Bible, Hindu mythology, translation of his works, his creativity and character requires consistent learning. In the translation of Jack London's stories "Love of Life" and "Mexican" from English to Uzbek, Professor F.Abdullaev translated personal names, geographical names and words reflecting national characteristics in accordance with the above rules. This translation corresponds to the original work. Here they are transliterated and translated:[7]

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Names transliterated: Bill-Bill, May Sethby-May Sethsby, Spider Hagerty-Spider Hagerty, Jose Amarillo-Joce Amarillo, Prayne-Prayne.[5] River, lake, desert, state, city names are also transliterated: Coppermine-Kappernmain, Hudson-Hudson, Mackenzie-Mackenzie, California-California, etc. Some place names are literally translated to introduce the reader: The Great Bear Lake, Land of little sticks.

As the writer tries to describe the events and events, it is natural that in his works many words and language elements representing the same events and events are used. For example, take the following passage from Jack London's story "Love of Life":

Once he crawled near the sick wolf. The animal dragged itself reluctantly out of its way, licking its chops with a tongue which seemed hardly to have the strength to curl. The man noticed that the tongue was not the usual healthy red. It was a yellowish brown and seemed coated with a rough and half-dry mucus (Jack London. "Love of life").

Translated by Fattoh Abdullaev:

Once he even got very close to a sick wolf. Reluctantly, the wolf moved aside and licked its muzzle, barely moving its tongue. His tongue is not red like that of a healthy wolf, but gray-yellow, covered with a thick mucus like glue (J. London. Stories. "Love of Life").

This image of the wolf in the quoted passage shows how close J. London is to the animal world, how he can feel the animal world from the heart, how strong is his knowledge of their psychology and living habits. To clearly show such ability, great work and art is required from the translator.

CONCLUSION

Jack London's "Martin Eden" is one of the literary masterpieces recognized by the world. This work was translated into Uzbek by Kadir Mirmuhammedov based on the edition published in 1961 in Moscow by the publishing house "Ogonyek". Its Uzbek version was published for the

first time in 1986 in the city of Tashkent in the fiction publishing house named after Gafur Gulam.

Some of Jack London's works express opinions against the theory of individualism of that time. His work "Martin Eden" is to some extent autobiographical. This work was written during J. London's North Sea voyage.

REFERENCES:

1. Anikin G.V. Istoriya angliskoy literature. – Moskva.: Nauka, 1975. – 56 p
2. Geismar, William. Articles. – London.: Lighthouse, 1986 y. – 89 p
3. Jek London. Martin Eden. London.: – Project – Gutenberg book, 2010 . – 15 p
4. Jek London. Martin Iden. – Toshkent.: – Gafur Gulom, 1986 – 31 p
5. Polatov. Yu. Badiiy asarda nomlar tarjimasi. – T.: Fan, 1967. – 28 p
6. Stone, Ingmar. A sailor in a raw. – Bern.: Wirschaft, 1988. – 14 p
O‘zbek tili adabiyoti 1962. – 89 p
7. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. <http://hikmatlar.uz>